

3D-PRINTED CORE REINFORCED WITH UNIDIRECTIONAL TAILORED FIBER PLACEMENT AND BRAIDED STRUCTURES FOR USE IN CUSTOM-MADE COMPOSITE KNEE ORTHOSES

Marcin Barburski¹, Jakub Szary¹, David Ranz²

¹Institute of Architecture of Textiles, Faculty of Material Technologies and Textile Design, Lodz University of Technology, Zeromskiego 116, 90-543 Lodz, Poland
Email: marcin.barburski@p.lodz.pl, web page: <https://p.lodz.pl/>

²Department of Design and Manufacture Engineering, University of Zaragoza, C/María de Luna, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain
Email: dranz@unizar.es, web page: <https://www.unizar.es/>

Keywords: Composite, Additive manufacturing, Tailored fibre placement, Knee orthosis, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

A custom-made approach to medical devices is crucial for delivering effective therapy and enhancing quality of life. However, producing devices tailored to individual needs presents unique challenges that differ significantly from mass production. These challenges include precise measurement, specialized modeling and design, and customized tooling.

In this study, we present CAD and FEM modeling, used to create custom knee orthoses. Research indicates that 3D-printed cores can be strengthened by adding an outer layer made from various textile structures, such as braids, knits, and woven fabrics [1, 2]. Additionally, UD fibers can be effectively integrated into composites through tailored fiber placement techniques [3].

For our application, the composite structure was built using an individually designed, 3D-printed core based on a 3D scan of a human leg, embroidered unidirectional (UD) glass fibers, and a braided carbon fiber tube, all infused with epoxy resin via the infusion method [4]. Tensile tests were conducted for each textile structure orientation to model the FEM of the composite knee brace.

Our research demonstrates that the new composite can be successfully used in custom-made orthoses, with specific strength comparable to the aluminum alloy commonly used in knee braces. Additionally, the successful development of an FEM model, which allows for the analysis of various reinforcement configurations within a quasi-elastic range, was validated through tensile test of the composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

A custom-made approach to medical devices plays a crucial role in delivering effective therapy and improving patients' quality of life. This is especially important for knee orthoses, which must address not only the biomechanical requirements of the user but also their unique anatomy. In recent years, additive manufacturing and composite technologies have attracted increasing attention as they enable the production of personalized medical devices with optimized mechanical properties.

Figure 1: Main components of a knee orthosis [1].

However, the design and manufacturing of custom-made orthoses pose numerous challenges that distinguish them from mass production. These challenges include the need for precise anatomical measurements, the development of individualized CAD models, strength analysis using finite element methods (FEM), and the selection of appropriate textile structures and technologies for their integration with the composite matrix.

Previous research indicates that reinforcing 3D-printed cores with textile structures—such as braids, knits, and woven fabrics—can significantly improve their mechanical properties [2, 3]. Moreover, precise techniques like tailored fiber placement allow unidirectional (UD) fibers to be integrated into composites in a way that maximizes their potential [4].

The aim of this study was to develop and investigate the properties of a novel composite knee orthosis structure, which incorporates an individually designed, 3D-printed core, tailored fiber placement UD glass fibers, and a braided carbon fiber sleeve, all used to build the frame of the orthosis. Mechanical tests and FEM analysis were carried out to evaluate the potential of this innovative construction for orthotic applications.

2 MATERIALS

2.1 Unidirectional glass fiber (UGF)

The unidirectional (UD) reinforcement was fabricated using tailored fiber placement (TFP) technology on a ZSK JCZA 0109-550 embroidery machine (Figure 1). Three layers of E-glass roving (density $\rho = 2.54 \text{ g/cm}^3$, linear density 600 tex, silane-sized, supplied by Krosoglass S.A.) were stitched onto a $280 \times 280 \text{ mm}$ polyester substrate with an areal density of 50 g/m^2 . Non-load-bearing threads were used for stitching: polyester $2 \times 10 \text{ tex}$ and polyamide 11 tex on the top side. The glass fibers were arranged at a density of 42 rovings per centimeter, with a stitch length of 4 mm. The total areal weight of the UD reinforcement was determined to be 2755 g/m^2 , comprising 2520 g/m^2 from the glass fibers, 120 g/m^2 from the polyester threads at the bottom, and 65 g/m^2 from the polyamide threads at the top.

Figure 1: Unidirectional E-glass textile reinforcements produced by tailored fiber placement (UGF).

2.2 Braided carbon fiber (BCF)

A 2×2 biaxial braided sleeve, shown in Figure 2, was manufactured from carbon fiber using 12K GRAFIL 34-700 rovings (density $\rho = 1.8 \text{ g/cm}^3$, linear density 800 tex) by Eurocarbon B.V. (reference D144/11). The fabric exhibited an areal weight of $665 \pm 10 \text{ g/m}^2$ and was braided at an angle of $\pm 30^\circ$, with a pick density of 20 picks per decimeter. For preparation, the braided tube was slit lengthwise and its edges were reinforced with tape to prevent fraying.

Figure 2: $\pm 30^\circ$ 2×2 biaxial braided carbon fiber sleeve (BCF).

2.3 Multi-layered composite (MLC)

Two types of textile reinforcements, UGF and BCF, were positioned on a 3D-printed (3DP) core and infused with resin under vacuum conditions. For the UGF layer, a strip measuring 30×250 mm was applied, while the BCF reinforcement used a smaller-diameter braided sleeve (Eurocarbon B.V., D-048-14, with an areal weight of 665 g/m^2 at a $\pm 30^\circ$ braid angle). Figure 3 presents a cross-sectional view illustrating the dimensions and stacking sequence of the composite structure.

Figure 3: Structure and dimensions of the Multi-Layered Composite (MLC).

The core was manufactured by powder bed fusion using an HP Jet Fusion 3D 4200 printer, employing Multi Jet Fusion (MJF) technology. PA12 powder served as the build material, processed with an 80/20 ratio of recycled to fresh powder. The layer thickness was set to 0.08 mm, and the balanced printing mode achieved a speed of $4115 \text{ cm}^3/\text{h}$ with solid infill. Components were spaced with a 5 mm gap, resulting in a packing density of 8.98%. The printed cores were oriented along the X-axis, and the final material density was measured at 1.01 g/cm^3 . Following the printing process, the cores underwent cleaning via sandblasting.

2.4 Composite preparations

The textile layers were arranged on a flat glass plate layered with peel-ply, infusion mesh, and a vacuum bag. Resin feed and evacuation points were set on opposite edges of the fabric assembly. For the MLC configuration, the resin inlet was located at the start of the core and the outlet at its far end. The infusion process employed a mixture of HAVEL Composite LH145 epoxy resin combined with HAVEL Composite H135 hardener at a 100:35 weight ratio. Following resin impregnation, the composites were cured at 25°C for at least 24 hours before being shaped and oriented for testing, with final cutting performed by water jetting.

3 METHODS

3.1 Tensile test

Tensile testing was performed following ISO 527-4 [6], with data analysis based on ISO 527-1 [7]. The tests utilized an INSTRON universal testing machine (Model 8982), operating at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. Five specimens from each configuration were tested until failure. Strain measurements were obtained using a 50 mm gauge-length extensometer. For UGF and MLC samples, the specimens measured $2.2 \times 25 \times 250$ mm, and the initial distance between grips was set at 150 mm. To reduce stress concentrations during testing, end tabs made of epoxy-impregnated carbon fiber twill were bonded to these samples. In the case of BCF specimens, due to the geometric constraints of the flattened braided sleeve, the dimensions were adjusted to 25×150 mm, and end tabs were omitted.

3.2 Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of MLC

The FEA of the MLC was performed using ANSYS APDL. A model was developed to accurately represent the mechanical behavior of the composite under tensile loading conditions. Key parameters were used to determine the stiffness matrix and to analyze the influence of different materials on the modulus of the MLC.

In the FEA model, one end of the specimen was fully fixed in all degrees of freedom to represent the stationary grip of the tensile testing machine. The opposite end was subjected to a displacement along the loading axis (Z-axis) corresponding to the maximum experimental strain. A quasi-static analysis was performed up to the elastic range identified in the experimental results.

Figure 4: Finite element analysis (FEA) model of Multi-Layered Composite (MLC).

The geometry of the MLC, presented in Figure 4 was defined by specifying the number of layers, their orientations, and thicknesses. A finite element mesh was generated using SOLID185 elements for the 3DP core and SHELL181 elements for the UGF and BCF reinforcements. Material properties were assigned to each layer, taking into account orthotropic elastic behavior.

4 RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

4.1 Tensile tests of composite layers

Tensile tests were performed on the UGF and BCF structures. The resulting tensile stress–strain curves are shown in Figure 5, while Table 1 provides a summary of their corresponding mechanical properties.

Figure 5: Tensile stress-strain curves of composite layers.

Parameter	UGF 00	UGF 90	BCF 00	BCF 45	BCF 90
Tensile strength σ_m [MPa]	730 \pm 44	12 \pm 1,5	219 \pm 16	64 \pm 5	39 \pm 2
Tensile strain ε_m [%]	2.3 \pm 0,2	1.3 \pm 0,2	0.8 \pm 0,1	0.4 \pm 0,1	0.8 \pm 0.1
Tensile modulus E_t [MPa]	32 860 \pm 485	5 870 \pm 450	35 880 \pm 1 570	18 950 \pm 1 430	7 060 \pm 240

Table 1: Tensile parameters of composite layers.

Significant differences in tensile strength were observed between the two structures. The UGF fabrics demonstrated approximately three times higher tensile strength in the 0° orientation compared to the

BCF braided structures, although the braided samples showed a tensile modulus about 8% higher. In the tested samples, only a single reinforcement layer was used, which had a substantial impact on the measured tensile properties.

It is important to note that in typical braided structures, fibers form a continuous pattern, whereas in rectangular tensile samples, fibers are cut, disrupting their continuity. During tensile loading, fibers can stretch and reorient along the applied force direction, particularly if they were initially set at an angle. This behavior affects the measured tensile strength and strain, meaning these parameters may not accurately represent the tensile strength of the braided structures. Moreover, research indicates that the initial modulus values for samples oriented at 0° and 90° are similar, suggesting comparable moduli in both directions despite differences in tensile strength [8].

4.2 Tensile tests of MLC

The MLC was fabricated using a 3D-printed core combined with two types of textile reinforcements, which were impregnated with epoxy resin. Tensile tests were then carried out on the prepared samples. Table 2 summarizes the key parameters of the MLC. Additionally, the accompanying graph highlights the Initial Linear Line (ILL), representing the elastic region of the MLC; here, ILL+ indicates the upper bound and ILL- the lower bound of the modulus.

Figure 6: Tensile stress-strain curves of the MLC.

Parameter	MLC
Tensile strength σ_m [MPa]	302 ±13
Tensile strain ε_m [%]	1.5 ±0.1
Tensile modulus E_t [MPa]	21 700 ±1 800

Table 2: Tensile parameters of the MLC.

The stress–strain response of the MLC displayed quasi-elastic behavior, with a slight reduction in slope detected between approximately 0.4% and 0.6% strain, as marked by the ILL. This reduction indicated a decrease in structural stiffness, although the composite still maintained its ability to bear loads. The carbon fiber layer was the first to fail, accompanied by the characteristic sound of carbon fiber fracture, which was evident in the graph as a further slope reduction around 1% strain. This abrupt failure of the carbon layer also led to the destruction of the 3D-printed core at a strain of about 1.5%. Following the failure of the BCF layer, the UGF reinforcement continued to support the load until it ultimately fractured, corresponding to the final drop in the stress–strain curve. The samples obtained after tensile and flexural testing are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Samples after tensile test. a) bottom view b) top view c) side view.

Figure 8 shows the specific strength and specific modulus of different materials, calculated as the ratio of the respective material property to its density. The MLC was assessed relative to the EN AW 6061 T6 aluminum alloy, commonly used in knee brace manufacturing, as well as the PA12 material produced using powder bed fusion technology [1, 8].

Figure 8: Comparison of the (a) specific strength and (b) specific modulus of various materials.

It is important to highlight that these parameters describe the materials as homogeneous structures and are intended solely for comparative purposes and assessing the potential of the new composite. While both aluminum and the MLC demonstrated the highest tensile strength, the MLC achieved a superior specific tensile strength, enhancing its effectiveness in applications where a high strength-to-weight ratio is essential. In terms of tensile modulus, the aluminum alloy showed a value approximately three times greater than that of the MLC. However, the stiffness of the composite could be increased by enlarging its cross-sectional area through the addition of extra FRC layers. When comparing specific modulus, the gap between aluminum and the MLC narrowed considerably to around 60%. The 3DP material displayed the lowest values across all parameters. Given that aluminum production requires expensive, single-use tooling, and that 3DP alone offers limited strength and stiffness, the MLC presents a promising solution for manufacturing custom-made components.

4.3 Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of MLC

The MLC was manufactured using a 3DP core with two types of textile reinforcements and infused with an epoxy resin. The samples underwent tensile testing, and the results were compared with the finite element model predictions, as presented in Figure 8 and summarized in Table 3.

Figure 9: Comparison of experimental and FEM tensile force–strain curves for the MLC.

Parameter	Experiment	FEM +30°/-30° Model	Error
Elastic modulus [MPa]	21 670 ±1 780	19 500	10%

Table 3: Comparison of tensile test results with FEM model.

The FEM simulations demonstrated a good correlation with the experimental results, showing only a 10% deviation in the elastic modulus, which confirms the reliability of the numerical model for predicting the behavior of various material configurations.

UD Configurations	Elastic modulus [MPa]	Difference vs. MLC
3DP/BCF/UD Carbon fiber	39 800	+104 %
3DP/BCF/UD Aramid	26 200	+34,4 %
3DP/BCF/UD Flax	15 900	-18,5 %

Table 4: Comparison of elastic moduli of different TFP UD reinforcements.

The analysis indicates that incorporating unidirectional carbon fibers could potentially double the modulus of the composite, significantly enhancing stiffness, while substituting flax fibers leads to a modest 18.5% reduction in modulus. This highlights the possibility of tailoring mechanical properties to specific applications and suggests that natural fibers like flax offer a promising, eco-friendly alternative for other applications.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated that the hybrid MLC composite, combining a 3D-printed core with tailored textile reinforcements, offers promising potential for use in personalized knee orthoses. The composite exhibited tensile strength comparable to aluminum while achieving approximately twice the specific tensile strength, indicating an excellent strength-to-weight ratio essential for lightweight medical

devices. Although the MLC's elastic modulus was three times lower than that of aluminum, the difference in specific modulus was significantly reduced, highlighting its suitability for applications requiring high stiffness-to-density performance.

Finite element simulations showed good agreement with experimental data, deviating by only 10% in elastic modulus, thereby validating the numerical model for predicting various material configurations. Furthermore, the analysis confirmed that incorporating carbon fibers as unidirectional layers could substantially increase the modulus, whereas using flax fibers resulted in only a moderate reduction of 18.5%, offering an environmentally friendly alternative. Overall, the presented approach enables the development of customized, high-performance orthopedic devices that can be tailored to individual anatomical and mechanical requirements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was carried out within the Ministry of Science and Higher Education project number DWD/5/0365/2021 "Doktorat wdrożeniowy V".

The authors acknowledge the project "Sustainable Industrial Design of Textile Structures for Composites," which is funded by the European Union. Grant Agreement no. 101079009 Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03/Twinning. Acronym: SustDesignTex.

REFERENCES

- [1] Follow Force; <https://qmedinfo.pl/pl/oferta/konczynna-dolna/staw-kolanowy/item/486-follow-orteza-stawu-kolanowego-z-regulacja-zakresu-ruchomosci>; 07.2025
- [2] Szary J, Barbuski M, Świniarski J. Mechanical properties of textile-reinforced composites with 3D printed core, *Fibres & Textiles in Eastern Europe*. 2023; 10.2478/fee-2023-0034
- [3] Ponięcka A, Barbuski M, Ranz D, Cuartero J, Miralbes R. Comparison of Mechanical Properties of Composites Reinforced with Technical Embroidery, UD and Woven Fabric Made of Flax Fibers. *Materials*. 2022 Oct 25;15(21):7469.
- [4] Szary J., Barbuski M., Mechanical Comparison and Practical Application of Composites with a 3D Printed Core and Textile Reinforcement, In: Conference Book of International Conference Innovatex 2023, p. 28-34, 22-24 November 2023.
- [5] Szary J., Barbuski M. Orteza stawu kolanowego, UPRP Patent pending PL442096A1, filed 26.08.2022 and issued 04.03.2024.
- [6] ISO 527-4:2021 - Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 4: Test conditions for isotropic and orthotropic fibre-reinforced plastic composites.
- [7] ISO 527-1:2019 - Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 1: General principles.
- [8] Cichosz J, Wehrkamp-Richter T, Koerber H, et al (2016) Failure and damage characterization of ($\pm 30^\circ$) biaxial braided composites under multiaxial stress states. *Compos Part Appl Sci Manuf* 90:748–759. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.08.002>.
- [9] Aluminum 6061-T6 datasheet, <https://www.matweb.com/>; 07.2025